

Supplementary Material

A validated model for early prediction of group A streptococcal aetiology and clinical endpoints in necrotising soft tissue infections

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Supplementary Note 2. Overview of hyperparameters tuned

Classification algorithms:

Logistic Regression (LR):

- *penalty*: none, l2
- *C*: 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1, 10, 100, 1000

Gaussian process classifier (GPC):

- *kernel*: DotProduct, Matern, RationalQuadratic, WhiteKernel

Gaussian Naive Bayes (GNB):

- *var_smoothing*: 100 steps from -9 until +9

Random Forest Classifier (RFC):

- *n_estimators*: 100, 300, 700
- *max_depth*: 2, 4, 6
- *max_features*: 2, 4, 6

Regression algorithms:

Lasso regression:

- *selection*: "random"
- *alpha*: 1.0, 0.7, 0.5

Ridge regression

- *alpha*: 1.0, 0.7, 0.5

Elastic nets:

- *l1_ratio*=0.5
- *selection*="random"
- *alpha*: 1.0, 0.7, 0.5

Multi-layer perceptron regression:

- *activation*: "relu"
- *batch_size*: 64
- *early_stopping*: True
- *solver*: "adam"
- *alpha*: 1, 0.1, 0.01, 0.001, 0.0001
- *hidden_layer_size*: (10, 3), (11, 3), (8, 3), (7, 3), (9, 3)

Random Forest Regressor:

- *n_estimators*: 100, 300
- *max_depth*: 2, 4
- *max_features*: 2, 4

Supplementary Figure 1. **Structured flowcharts detailing the (a) developmental and validation process of the machine learning models (b) time-dependent data dissection.** (a) This conceptual pipeline was systematically implemented for every clinical outcome assessed. External validation was exclusively pursued concerning the bacterial etiology (presence of Group A Streptococcus). (b) The INFECT study cohort was split into the time-dependent subsets *entry*, *pre-* and *post-surgery* at referral center, *baseline*, depending on the clinical availability of the data. n: number of patients/iterations; LOOCV: leave-one-out cross-validation; LR: logistic regression, GPC: Gaussian process classifier, GNB: Gaussian naive bayes; RFC: Random Forest classifier; Lasso: Lasso regression, Ridge: Ridge regression, EN: elastic net regression, GPR: Gaussian process regression, MLP: multi-layer perceptron; RFR: Random Forest regression.

Supplementary Figure 2. **Comparison performance between different time-dependent datasets for the estimation of the presence of GAS.** (left) ROC curve (right) Precision-Recall curve. ENTRY (upon hospital admission), PRESURGERY (prior to first surgical procedure), POSTSURGERY (posterior to first surgical procedure and prior to ICU admission), BL (baseline; first 24 h of ICU admission). AUC: Area under the ROC curve, AP: average precision.

Supplementary Figure 3. **SHAP dependence plots** for (a) age (b) creatinine (c) haemoglobin. The colour gradient denotes the variable values, with red indicating high values (e.g. age ~ 70 years) and blue indicating low values (e.g. age ~ 20 years).

Supplementary Figure 4. **SHAP values for models estimating the presence of GAS with the external validation cohort.** Variables are sorted from most impactful (top, creatinine) to least impactful (bottom, diabetes), with every dot representing a patient. Positive SHAP values for a variable indicate a positive contribution to the model's decision to identify the patient as GAS-positive. Conversely, negative SHAP values indicate a contribution to classifying the patient as GAS-negative. The colour gradient denotes the variable values, with red indicating high values (e.g. age ~ 70 years) and blue indicating low values (e.g. age ~ 20 years).

Supplementary Table 1: **Overview for the number of patients included and data subsets assessed for each clinical outcome.**

Outcome category	Outcome	No. of patients (n)	Time-dependent data subsets	Prediction task	No. of patients (%) or mean \pm SD
causative microbes	Presence of GAS	409	Entry, pre-surgery, post-surgery, baseline	classification (y/n)	126 (30.8%)
	Risk of amputation	409	Entry, pre-surgery	classification (y/n)	54 (13.2%)
surgical aspects	Size of skin defect (after first surgery)	391	Entry, pre-surgery	regression (pct. of body surface)	4.9 \pm 5.2
	Size of skin defect (maximal)	409	Post-surgery, baseline	regression (pct. of body surface)	6.4 \pm 7.3
patient management	Length of ICU stay	402	Entry, pre-surgery, post-surgery, baseline	regression (days)	10.7 \pm 10.8
organ support	Need for RRT (within 24h after ICU admission)	409	Entry, pre-surgery, post-surgery	classification (y/n)	57 (13.9%)

Supplementary Table 2: Summary of number of patients and variables in each time-dependent data subset. Details on the timeline indicating the timing of each categorised clinical variable collected can be found in Supplementary Figure 2.

	No. of patients (n)	No. of variables (n)
Entry	409	45
Pre-surgery	409	56
Post-surgery	409	723
Baseline	409	762

Supplementary Table 3: **Detailed description for variables used in the estimation of the presence of GAS.**

Variable name	Description
age	age at admission [years]
affected: upper arm	affection of upper arm ¹ [y/n]
affected: lower arm	affection of lower arm ¹ [y/n]
affected: anogenital area	affection of anogenital area ¹ [y/n]
surgery before	surgery within 4 weeks previous of NSTI [y/n]
diabetes	diabetes [y/n]
creatinine (preop)	Highest preoperative ² creatinine [$\mu\text{mol/L}$]
haemoglobin (preop)	Lowest preoperative ² haemoglobin [mmol/L]
creatinine (preadmission)	Highest preadmission ³ creatinine [$\mu\text{mol/L}$]
Lowest systolic BP (BL)	Lowest BL ⁴ systolic blood pressure [mmHg]
Creatinine (BL)	Highest BL ⁴ creatinine [$\mu\text{mol/L}$]
Noradrenaline (BL)	Highest noradrenaline infusion rate at BL ⁴ [$\mu\text{g/kg/min}$]
Platelets (BL)	Lowest BL ⁴ platelets [$10^9/\text{L}$]
Lactate (BL)	Highest BL ⁴ lactate level [mmol/L]
Glucose (BL)	Highest BL ⁴ glucose [mmol/L]
Anatomical site sampled	Anatomical site ⁵ specimen was sampled from

¹ at arrival at sepcialized hospital

² before the first surgery, which is before ICU admission

³ upon ICU admission

⁴ during the first 24 hours in the ICU

⁵ one of the following: head/neck, u. arm, l. arm, hand, finger, thorax, abdomen, ano-gen., u. leg, l. leg, foot, toe

Supplementary Table 4. **Performance comparison of several machine learning-based classifiers for the prediction of GAS aetiology for each time-dissected data subset.** Displayed are the mean performances across leave-one-out cross-validation (LOOCV). log: Logistic Regression, gpc: Gaussian Process Classifier, rfc: Random Forest Classifier, Acc.: balanced accuracy, Prec.: precision, Brier: Brier score, ROC AUC: area under the receiver-operator curve, Ave. prec.: average precision

Entry						
Model	Prec.	Recall	F1-score	Acc.	ROC AUC	Ave. prec.
log	0.520	0.825	0.638	0.743	0.792	0.595
gpc	0.517	0.825	0.636	0.741	0.794	0.608
rfc	0.524	0.857	0.651	0.755	0.804	0.604
Pre-surgery						
Model	Prec.	Recall	F1-score	Acc.	ROC AUC	Ave. prec.
log	0.582	0.762	0.660	0.759	0.825	0.659
gpc	0.551	0.810	0.656	0.758	0.827	0.646
rfc	0.633	0.738	0.681	0.774	0.838	0.704
Post-surgery						
Model	Prec.	Recall	F1-score	Acc.	ROC AUC	Ave. prec.
log	0.643	0.714	0.677	0.769	0.840	0.674
gpc	0.652	0.730	0.689	0.779	0.850	0.693
rfc	0.617	0.794	0.694	0.787	0.839	0.700
Baseline						
Model	Prec.	Recall	F1-score	Acc.	ROC AUC	Ave. prec.
log	0.593	0.810	0.685	0.781	0.844	0.660
gpc	0.674	0.722	0.697	0.783	0.860	0.704
rfc	0.757	0.619	0.681	0.765	0.846	0.704

Supplementary Table 5. **Model performances in estimating GAS involvement for time-dissected datasets.** Depicted are the mean and the 95% confidence intervals (in parentheses). Acc.: balanced accuracy, Prec.: precision, Brier: Brier score, ROC AUC: area under the receiver-operator curve, Ave. prec.: average precision

	Entry	Pre-surgery	Post-surgery	Baseline	Pre-surgery (fine-tuned)
Acc.	0.652 (0.574,0.735)	0.726 (0.642,0.796)	0.723 (0.644,0.791)	0.727 (0.658,0.799)	0.677 (0.617, 0.737)
Prec.	0.572 (0.435,0.724)	0.666 (0.548,0.784)	0.683 (0.556,0.811)	0.729 (0.600,0.867)	0.644 (0.534, 0.776)
Recall	0.463 (0.267,0.698)	0.583 (0.391,0.739)	0.564 (0.396,0.720)	0.547 (0.396,0.700)	0.568 (0.417, 0.726)
F1-score	0.502 (0.351,0.632)	0.617 (0.483,0.719)	0.613 (0.486,0.714)	0.621 (0.500,0.729)	0.598 (0.509, 0.682)
Brier	0.170 (0.142,0.203)	0.152 (0.128,0.183)	0.149 (0.125,0.180)	0.147 (0.125,0.172)	0.199 (0.168, 0.238)
ROC AUC	0.794 (0.733,0.851)	0.828 (0.763,0.883)	0.836 (0.775,0.891)	0.839 (0.779,0.894)	0.758 (0.697, 0.817)
Ave. prec	0.617 (0.494,0.719)	0.684 (0.568,0.787)	0.685 (0.570,0.788)	0.703 (0.592,0.807)	0.701 (0.604, 0.780)

Supplementary Table 6. **Overview of variables yielded through unsupervised variable selection** for prediction of surgical, patient management, and organ support outcomes. BMI: Body Mass Index, BL: baseline (24 hours after ICU admission), CRP: c-reactive protein, preop: preoperative, KDIGO: Kidney Disease Improving Global Outcomes, WBC: white blood cell count,

Risk of amputation	Size of skin defect (after first surgery)	Size of skin defect (maximal)	Days spent in ICU	Need for RRT (24h after ICU admission)	Need for RRT (90 days)
Weight	Weight	BP (highest BL)	No. of blood samples taken	Weight	Pulse (lowest BL)
Height	Height	Bilirubin (highest BL)	Discoloration (preop)	Height	Carbamid (highest BL)
Discoloration (preop)	Bullae (preop)	No. of blood samples (1st surgery)	WBC (preop)	Discoloration (preop)	Kalium (highest BL)
Bruising (preop)	WBC (preop)	Blood collection mode	CRP (preop)	WBC (preop)	Bicarbonate (lowest BL)
WBC (preop)	CRP (preop)	Bullae (preop)	creatinine (preop)	CRP (preop)	Urine output (BL)
CRP (preop)	creatinine (preop)	WBC (preop)	Haemoglobin (preop)	creatinine (preop)	creatinine (preop)
creatinine (preop)	Natrium (preop)	Blood products (baseline)	Age	Natrium (preop)	creatinine (BL)
Natrium (preop)	Haemoglobin (preop)	Center code	affected: head/neck	Haemoglobin (preop)	Noradrenaline (max BL)
Haemoglobin (preop)	BMI	Bullae (during 1st surgery)	Varicella	BMI	pH (lowest BL)
BMI	Center code	Haemoglobin (preop)	Size of skin defect (after first surgery)	Age	SBE (lowest BL)
Age	Age	CRP (preop)		affected: upper leg	Lactate (highest BL)
	affected: abdomen			Cardiovascular disease present	Crystalloids (BL)
	affected: upper leg				Accumulated fluids (BL)
	affected: lower leg				KDIGO stage
					creatinine (preadmission)
					WBC (preop)
n = 11	n = 14	n = 11	n = 10	n = 12	n = 16

Supplementary Table 7. **Prediction performance for clinical endpoints revolving around surgical aspects, patient management, and organ support.** Ave. prec. : average precision, R² coefficient of determination, MAE: mean absolute error, MSE: mean squared error

	Risk of amputation	Size of skin defect (after first surgery)	Size of skin defect (maximal)	Days spent in ICU	Need for RRT (24h after ICU admission)
Acc.	0.503 (0.483, 0.546)	-	-	-	0.543 (0.493, 0.610)
Prec.	0.137 (0.000, 1.000)	-	-	-	0.467 (0.000, 1.000)
Recall	0.020 (0.000, 0.106)	-	-	-	0.109 (0.000, 0.250)
F1-score	0.033 (0.000, 0.182)	-	-	-	0.168 (0.000, 0.345)
Brier	0.113 (0.092, 0.136)	-	-	-	0.105 (0.083, 0.125)
Ave. prec.	0.261 (0.159, 0.411)	-	-	-	0.385 (0.238, 0.540)
R²	-	0.120 (0.044, 0.178)	0.179 (0.100,0.234)	0.018 (-0.063,0.056)	-
MAE	-	3.500 (3.144, 3.831)	4.383 (3.905, 4.879)	7.047 (6.194,7.976)	-
MSE	-	24.086 (16.334, 34.611)	43.328 (27.789, 66.054)	111.952 (65.077, 172.308)	-